

THE INFLUENCE OF THE PSYCHO-COGNITIVE AND SOCIO-CULTURAL FACTORS IN THE PROCESS OF THE REALIZATION OF UNDERSTANDING IN READINGⁱ

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Abstract:

In the last two decades, we have observed a clear and growing interest in the didactics and assessment of *meaningful reading* as an indication of linguistic sub-competence. Many scholars have considered it as a complex and multidimensional process because *understanding* was considered in a large percentage the reason for a student's success or failure and in many respects it constitutes the criterion for being considered a literate or educated person. This study is focused on the problems of implementing the teaching of *meaningful reading* as a psychological phenomenon. If the scholars agree on the definition of *meaningful reading*, the on-going instructional debate has to do with the finding of a kind of consensus on the realization of meaning in reading. It is difficult to achieve a full understanding of the meaning of the cognition and metacognition processes, due to their indeterminate nature. Nevertheless, the data from the research literature in the field of reading competence indicate that there exists a growing consensus concerning the effective teaching practices, in addition to the pedagogical models, and this is very promising for the improvement of *meaningful reading* skills. The aim of this study is to argue for the best psycho-pedagogical models, which constitute the basis of finding a growing consensus of the best practices of effectively teaching *meaningful reading*. The most representative models of the study of *meaningful reading* are divided into three main categories: Models of Cognitive Psychology, those of Socio-cultural Psychology and those of Social-cognitive Psychology. In the didactic practice of learning *meaningful reading*, certain interactive reading process models are

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used. These are oriented towards the mental processes of learning in a continuous exchange of information between the student and the text, as well as towards the social-cultural linguistic factors of the text (the functional grammar of the text) conditioned by the situational context of the communication. The holistic contemporary model of the *meaningful reading* process is built on the basis of these models. The problems raised have to do with two factors: *first*, is the teaching of *meaningful reading* mostly focused on the grammar of the text? Or *second*, on the activation of higher-order thinking skills which engage the learner's critical thinking skills?

Realization of the study: in order to study the didactic approaches and influences on *meaningful reading* (as a dependent variable), two independent variables have been determined: (a.) linguistic-social-cultural factors of the text (i.e. *the functional grammar of the text*) conditioned by the social-cultural context of the communication. (b.) The reflective mental activities utilized to understand the meaning of the text (graphic organizers and *Higher-order thinking*). This study will analyse the influence of the linguistic socio-cultural factors of the text and that of the Higher-order thinking skills of the student-reader on the development of critical thinking while reading, based on the didactic activities of teaching in the book of Albanian language 6-9.

The method of research is the study of the relations between the factors as a cause and effect relationship type through the results of statistical processing of quantitative and qualitative data using the software SPSS (version 21).

Keywords: linguistic competence, meaningful reading, samples of meaning realization, the reader, the text and the context

Introduction

After the year 1990, academic interest in the study of language has been focused on the communicative function according to the text-based approach. Teaching and learning language at school now takes a special significance, as the instructional interest shifts from the lesson focused on language as an object of study, to the treatment of language as a cross-curricular descriptive competence of the overall school programme (language and multi-literacy\ -ies across the curriculum). The competency of communication in language involves three dimensions: (1). A communication dimension; the skill to use and understand language in authentic situations. (2). A text-based linguistic dimension; the learning of grammatical phenomena in complete structured texts for a concrete intention. (3). A critical thinking dimension; the skill of the students to understand and to produce different kinds of texts as well as to build their own knowledge.

The interest of this study is focused on the treatment of *meaningful reading* as a linguistic sub-competence wherein *comprehension* is considered in large part the reason for success or failure of the students, constituting the criterion for someone to be considered literate. The scientific discussions and studies on the meaning of reading, reading for learning and teaching of reading, have become more complicated and sometimes also confusing. Despite that, a growing consensus has been observed concerning the best practices of effective teaching, in addition to the pedagogical models, which means that classroom teachers must mix the best elements of these models. The interactive reading process models of the cognitive and social-constructive psychology are among the best teaching models when the goal is reading for comprehension. These models differ regarding which factor they emphasize the most. The common point is the conceptualization of reading as a process of active interaction of the reader with the text, conditioned by the social-cultural context of communication.

The research studies on *meaningful reading* identified and confirmed the difficulties students have related to the different kinds of texts, types of reading methods, the intention for which a text was written, overemphasis on language learning (mainly of literary texts), exercises of a transformative type and the learning of metalanguage, etc. This encouraged scholars to focus their attention on the study of the procedures which produce the written discourse. *Meaningful reading* constitutes a complex cerebral and creative activity which demands motivation and claims, in addition to the great mnemonic skill, also the synchronized activation of many cognitive processes. The text should be conceptualized as a social-cultural creation which drives at the writer's intention and the reader's perception. The text is perceived as the writer's text and the reader's text. As a result, different kinds of texts end up in different schemes of thinking, understanding and creating. This directed the attention of the scholars to the treatment of such issues as: the selection of different types of text, the functional grammar of the text (structure, style, social-cultural context, writer, reader, etc), and the reflective mental procedure upon the text's content and meaning, etc.

Literary competence in reading

The Programme of the Albanian Language develops the competence of communication through the intertwining of five themes which function in unison: reading, writing, listening, speaking and knowledge of the linguistic system. In the new instructional programme of Albanian Language, 6-9, 2014, the linguistic sub-competence in reading

is realized through the section, “*Reading literary and non-literary texts*.ⁱⁱ” In the new instructional program of Albanian language, the sub-competence of *meaningful reading* is described as follows: The students read literary and non-literary texts which belong to different periods, both classic and contemporary texts of Albanian and world literature and they demonstrate the meaning, the interpretation and analysis and the evaluation and judgement based on these texts (suitable for the age development of the students). With the reformation of the Albanian Educational System after the year 2000, there is an observable shift from the traditional concept of rigidly learning the grammar of the linguistic system, towards a more functional, text-based approach to linguistic study.

Levels of understanding in reading

Kintsch, W. (2002) refers to three levels of understanding a text:

- a. Superficial understanding (the surface level). It is understanding of the words, phrases or diagrams, without going deep into understanding. In this level, the student may remember a few words or phrases from the text.
- b. Basic understanding (the text-based level). It is the semasiological structure which stems from the text without the consideration of other elements which are not discussed directly in the text (i.e. the core content itself).
- c. Situational or contextual understanding (the situational/contextual level), is the full and detailed understanding of the text. In this case, the student should make the connection between the existing knowledge and prior knowledge in order to build the full meaning of the text, completely and coherently within the social-cultural context, or the intention for which it is written by the author.

Theoretical models on the realization of *meaningful reading*

Three primary groupings are observed concerning the theoretical analysis of contemporary literature as it relates to the educational debate on the process of realization of meaningful reading: (a) cognitive models, (b) social-cultural models and (c) social-cognitive models.

a. Cognitive models

According to Cognitive Psychology, understanding is achieved through an active process whereby the reader tries to create mental representations of the text at a micro-

ⁱⁱhttp://www.arsimi.gov.al/files/userfiles/kurrikula/PROGRAMI_GJUHE_SHQIPE,_shkalla_3.pdf

level (using words and sentences) and macro-level (using semasiological meaning and text structure).

b. Social-Cultural models

The development of cognitive skills in writing and reading to facilitate learning are not a simple psychological process, but more so a social-psychological activity. According to Vigotsky 1978, the social factor precedes the individual factor and consolidates the cognitive factor. Spoken and written text is considered dependent on social parameters of communication. Meanwhile, in the moment of its articulation, it creates new parameters and consequences. The contemporary social-cultural viewpoints on understanding texts rely on Halliday's linguistic semiotic-functional theory and on the movement of pedagogy according to the text-based approach. His theory is focused on the kind of text as a means to conduct analysis and learn language at school. The basic linguistic concept is that of a social semiotic system, on which meanings are built and exchanged and which is directly related to social reality. According to this theory the meaning of the texts stem from the linguistic relationships within the text as well as from the interaction of the text with the social contexts to which it refers. In this way, written discourse is simply the active use of the text in various communication contexts. The basic linguistic and social-cultural components used to build meaning are: Language (both text and context). Language, according to semiotic-social conceivability, produces meaning during its use through different kinds and types of text. The organization and structures of texts become the focus of study object, not simply the isolated components, such as words and sentences. The meaning of the text becomes negotiable through the elements of *style*, i.e. linguistic social-semasiologic variants (Halliday 1989). Through this component is interpreted the systematic relation between the text and the context, or between the text and the social practice that the text actualizes.

According to Halliday, the style is determined by the elements of the context of communication (context of situation) and namely: (1.) the field of instruction (or *field of discourse*), thus, what happens? (2.) The contextual roles of the interlocutors engaged in the communication (*tenor of discourse*), namely who takes part in the discourse? (3.) The method of instruction (*mode of discourse*), thus, how are the meanings exchanged and negotiated (Halliday 1989). These three factors affect the context of the selected language and influence the construction of the text. *The field* represents the representative metafunctioning of our experience in the world (ideational metafunction); *interlocutory roles* are related with the interpersonal function of the semasiologic system of language; *the way of the discourse type* is related with the textual

semasiologic metafunction, the way through which language functions as an instrument of structuring the message in relation with the holistic process of communication (Halliday 1989).

The theory of the stylistic field evolves further with the concept of the text genre. The theoreticians of text genres aim at rejoining language with its social context in a more systematic way for school education. The text genre constitutes a category which describes the relationship between a text's social-cultural aims and the organized structure of its meaning (Cope & Kalantzis 1993). There exists in every culture multiple and various text genres, each of them serving a different social aim.

c. Social-cognitive models

According to the social-cognitive models, understanding of a text is realized in a social-cognitive environment of learning. The *meaningful reading* is conceptualized as a complex dynamic process during which meet the cognitive, linguistic and social factors as well as respective skills. Learning environment is focused on the student's mental processes as well as on the text's social-linguistic factors which determine understanding as a social-cultural process conditioned by the context of communication.

Contemporary model of *meaningful reading*

Understanding a given text from both the traditional and contemporary points of view

The contemporary model differs from the traditional model in two aspects:

a. In the traditional model the *message* of the text is received in a passive way and in the reproduction of the words of the text as an entirety of hierarchic skills. In the contemporary model, the understanding is perceived as a building process and is built with the reader's active involvement and interaction with the text. The reading skills are conceived as a grouping of skills acting in concert, which gain meaning from the context of the communication.

b. *The role of the reader* in understanding a given text has evolved. In the traditional model the meaning existed inside the text as determined by the writer. The reader simply had to discover it. In the contemporary model, the reader instead builds the meaning of the text than reproduces the words of the text.

The process of building the meaning of the text presupposes the intertwining of several factors: (1) experiences of the reader in the reading situation; (2) characteristics of the written text; (3) text content, which determines the duty and the aim of the writer

and reader; (4) the reader's mental structures in the process of building the meaning of the text; (5) environment learning.

Figure 1: Interrelation of the basic components of the meaningful reading model

Source: The Author

Contemporary textual viewpoint of reading in order to understand

Based on the best theoretical models on the realization of understanding in reading, in the contemporary point of view, understanding in reading is conceived as an intertwining of three basic components: text, reader and class environment (Figure 1). (Irwin 1986). Reading involves the use of judgment, of critical thinking, understanding and communication. *Meaningful reading* is necessary in all the cognitive functions, such as problem solving and decision making. (McNamara, 2009).

The text refers to the reading material and it can be analyzed from four viewpoints: (a) writer's intention; (b) structure; (c) content and (d) situating in context. The writer's intention determines also the orientation of the other elements (Schraw, 1998). Both the writer's intention and genre of the text determine the context of the communication when it is read. They may be texts for personal or private use, for public use, or for educational use, etc. The writer may desire to act in the reader's emotional sphere, their cognitive sphere, or to influence the reader's volitional behaviour by orienting the reader a certain way, etc.

The reading factor constitutes the most complex component of understanding in the model. The reader realizes the process of *meaningful reading* through the cognitive and emotional structures they have at their disposal. They also implement procedures which will assist them in understanding the text.

Figure 2: Interaction of the factor Reader with *Procedures* and *Structures*

Source: The Author

Statistical analysis

In order to carry out the statistical study we gathered primary data by means of a questionnaire (survey). The survey was conducted by the teachers of language and literature who teach these two subjects in the Schools of Gjirokastra. The District of Gjirokastra, which in general constitutes the environment (survey population) which we are studying, has in general 85 teachers in the field of language and literature. The focus of our study is not the demographic distribution of *Critical thinking in reading*; for this reason we were contented with the selection of an easily accessible sample group which ensures the requisite number for a statistical representation of the population. We included 29 teachers of languages and literature in our study. They constitute 34% of the population of all the teachers of this school subject.

The empirical study of data aimed at statistically studying and determining the relations between the dependant variable *Critical thinking in reading* and two other factors: (1) the text (*functional grammar of text and communication*) and (2) *advance organizer & higher-order thinking*, which are treated as independant variables. Such conceptualisation of the treatment of critical thinking in reading was realized based on a) the analysis of texts of albanian language used in middle schools (6-9) and b) the argumentative analysis of contemporary literature of the social-cognitive theoretical model (Flower, 1994) of the realization of meaningful reading in the subject matter albanian language. The independant variable *functional grammar of text and communication* (the social cultural-linguistic factors of the text) was realized based on the linguistic systemic-cultural theory (Halliday 1989) and on the systemic-functional model for language learning and teaching (Rothery 1994). Independant variable 2

advance organizer and higher-order thinking, represents the mental procedures of processing text. (see Figure 2).

The dependant variable is directly represented in the instrument used for data collection by means of question P₄ (see *Questionnaire*). It is measured by the principle of the division of the level of teachers' perception into three levels: *Little* = 1; *Satisfactory* = 2; *Considerable* = 3. The two other factors which are treated as independent variables are represented in the questionnaire by a group of questions which measure the teachers' level of perception according to the above three levels (see Table 1 and *Questionnaire*). For this reason, both independent variables are measured by means of real values provided as simple arithmetic averages of the respective ordinal values of questions they represent.

Table 1: Variables, their labeling and measuring

Kind of Variable	Name of Variable	The Questions which Represent It	The Way of Measuring
Dependent Variables	Critical thinking in reading	P ₄	Perception level according to Likert scale (1-3)
Independent Variables	Linguistic and social-cultural factors of communication (Functional grammar of text and communication)	P _{1a,1b,P2a,2b,2c,2d} P _{3a,3b, 3c,3d,3e}	Arithmetic average of the values of answers for the questions which they represent measured with Likert scale (1-3)
	Advance organizers & higher Order Thinking (Mental processing activities)	P _{10, P5a,b,c,d,e,}	Arithmetic average of the values of answers for the questions which they represent measured with Likert scale (1-3)

The main method used to study the statistical data and verify the hypotheses through results that this method enables is the type of cause-consequence relationship. The cause-consequence relationships are a general model of the analysis used by inferential statistics. They are classified into two main groups: (i) statistical relations (correlations) between independent variables and (ii) functional relations (regressive equations) between dependent variable and independent variables. Statistical relations aim at determining the correlative relationships between independent variables, whereas the functional relations aim at identifying the level of influence of each of the variables on the dependent variable as well as building a representative model offered by the sample selected for study. A part of statistical study is also the descriptive analysis of the data with the intention of reaching as clear as possible conclusions on the results of statistical elaboration in general. Statistical processing of data is realized using the software SPSS

version 21. Summarizing it in steps, the process of statistical study of the work is submitted to the algorithm presented in Figure 3.

Figure 3: The diagram of statistical study of the data

Our study aims at giving an answer to the question: *What is the extent of the influence on the development of critical thinking in reading (a) of the activation of the student's higher-order thinking? (b) How much does the study of a text's functional grammar influence the student's understanding of a text (linguistic social-cultural factors of the genre of the text) through the active interaction of the student with the text? (In teaching of meaningful reading, classes 6-9)*

In order to provide an answer to the above research questions, we have built the statistical hypotheses:

Hypothesis zero (H_0): The linguistic socio-cultural factors of text and Advance organizer and higher order thinking factors *do not* exercise any influence on Critical thinking in reading.

Alternative hypothesis (H_a): The linguistic socio-cultural factors of text and advance organizer and higher order thinking factors *do* exercise influence on critical thinking in reading.

The verification of hypotheses is made by means of the model offered by the study of functional relations through coefficients of linear regression, thus when the coefficients of regression are simultaneously zero then it is accepted that hypothesis H_0 is true, in any other case alternative hypothesis H_a is accepted.

The results for the elements of descriptive statistics, determined by the elaboration of the data presented in Table 2, indicate that the average of the observed values for *Critical thinking in reading* (variable (Y), is significantly above the theoretical average of probable values that this variable may take, whereas for the two other variables, *The social-cultural linguistic factors of communication* (X_1) and *Strategies and skills*

of *meaningful reading* (X_2), is below the theoretical average provided by the probable values for these variables. Thus, knowing that the probable values, or otherwise, probable alternatives to respond to the questions that these variables represent, are 1 to 3, they have an arithmetic (theoretical) average equal 2. For these variables we have noticed that the average observed only for the dependent variable is above the theoretical average ($Y = 2.21$), whereas for the two independent variables it is below the theoretical average ($X_1=1.90$; $X_2=1.98$).

Table 2: Elements of Descriptive Statistics

	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Critical thinking in reading	1.00	3.00	2.2143	.56811
The social – cultural linguistic factors of text (Text’s functional grammar)	1.29	2.43	1.9014	.28761
Advance organizer and higher order thinking (Data processing activities)	1.43	2.67	1.9817	.29864

Source: Output of SPSS v.21

But, in the three cases, as it can be seen also in the table, the observed average is very close to the theoretical average, which means that we have no appearance of tendencies of maximization of anyone of them. The sustainability of this phenomenon is strengthened by the low value of deviation which in our worst case is $s(Y_2)=0.57$. The result of descriptive statistics for the variables which take part in the research study indicates the average levels of perception on the social-cultural linguistic factors and advance organizer and higher order thinking are associated with an average level of the result for *Critical thinking in reading*.

The observed correlation in relationships (see Table 3) between the variables which take part in the verification of the hypothesis indicates that we have a strong statistical significance ($0.01 < p < 0.05$) in the calculation of the correlation coefficient (PCC=0.603) between the independent variables. This indicates that *both the independent variables develop their values in the same direction*.

Table 3: Correlative matrix for variables

		Social-cultural Factors of communication
Advance organizer and higher order thinking	Pearson Correlation	.603**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.001

Source: Output of SPSS v.21

It can be observed that the level of the values of PCC-s between these variables, does not pass the threshold (PCC >0.8) of the risk of the phenomena of multicollinearity*, which would bring anomalies in the calculation of linear regression parameters. Therefore, based on the meaning of multicollinearity, the model we have chosen to employ for the verification of statistical hypothesis is correct.

From the data elaboration, the model we have used shows the calculation of the linear regression coefficients make verification of the statistical hypothesis possible. In Table 4 we notice that the coefficients β_i are different from zero, a fact which proves the constancy of the alternative hypothesis. Thus, the data collected from the teachers' sample indicates that *The linguistic socio-cultural factors of text* and *Advance organizer and Higher Order Thinking* factors are a significant influence on *Critical thinking in reading*.

Table 4: Results of the linear regression model

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t
	B	Std. Error	Beta	
(Constant)	1.081	.810		1.334
The functional grammar of the text	.535	.475	.270	1.127
Higher order thinking (Data processing activities)	.056	.449	.030	.124

Source: Output of SPSS v.21

The results of the linear regression model, in addition to the verification of statistical hypothesis, make possible the statistical evaluation of the nature and level of influence of each independent variable on the dependent variable. Thus, we notice that $\beta_1 = 0.535 > 0$, which means that the independent linguistic *Socio-cultural factors of the text* exercise a positive influence on the dependant variable *advance organizer and higher order thinking*. In the same way, the independent variable *Strategies and skills of meaningful reading* increases the level of *Critical thinking in reading* by exercising a positive influence on it $\beta = 0.056 > 0$

Figure 4: Comparison of the level of influence of the independent factors

Source: The Author

Linear regression coefficients (see Figure 4) express also the level of the influence of each of the regressors on *Critical thinking in reading*. Figure 4 represents a chart showing the level of influence of each of the independent variables on the dependant variable. A simple calculation shows that *The linguistic socio-cultural factors of text* exercise a positive influence on *Critical thinking in reading* that is almost 10 times greater than the other factor, *Advance organizer and Higher Order Thinking*.

Figure 5: Generalizing model of the “Critical Thinking in Reading” variable

Source: Output of SPSS v.21

Inferential statistical studies, in addition to the results acquired for the sample studied, offer the opportunity to create more general models. In the results of descriptive statistics we notice that the observed average of *Critical thinking in reading* is 2.21, with a standard deviation of $s(Y) = 0.57$. Statistical elaboration of the data shows that the dependant variable, under the simultaneous influence of the two independent

variables, provides a generalizing model (Figure 5) with a mathematical expectation of the dependant, *Critical thinking in reading*, lower than that observed [$E(Y) = 1.94$] and almost on the same levels with the observed averages for independent variables. This result makes the conclusion reached from the descriptive statistics more durable: the average levels of perception on the linguistic socio-cultural factors of text and advance organizer and higher order thinking are associated with an average level of the result of *The critical thinking in reading*.

Conclusions

In summarizing the results of the statistical study of the data collected by the sample of teachers of the language and literature in Gjirokastra, we may say that:

- i. There exists a close relation between *The critical thinking in reading* expressed through the perception according to the Likert scale from 1 to 3 and two other factors which influence the meaningful reading: *Data processing activities* and the *Socio-cultural factors of communication*.
- ii. The linguistic-socio-cultural factors of text exercise a positive influence on *Critical thinking in reading* almost 10 times higher than the other factor *Advance organizer and higher order thinking*.
- iii. The average value observed (2.21) of the critical thinking in reading differs significantly from the mathematical expectation (1.94) offered by the model built with the observed data. But the generalizing model concludes that the average level of perception on the linguistic and social cultural factors of communication and advance organizer and higher order thinking are associated with an average level of the result for *Critical thinking in reading*.

This conceptualization in the treatment of critical thinking in reading was determined based (a.) on the analysis of the Albanian language texts for the higher and lower educational levels (6-9) and (b.) on the argumentative analysis of contemporary literature on the theoretical meaning in the subject matter of Albanian language.

The study result indicates that there is a high sensitiveness on the teachers' part towards the text factor in its holistic meaning. This is explained by the fact that the teachers of middle schools lack the appropriate experience and education about the contemporary pedagogical trends of language teaching according to the text-based approach, which is still unconsolidated and its infancy in Albania. On the other hand, considering the fact that they consider it as an instructional innovation, they have the tendency to embrace it without due consideration. An uncertainty is observed in the teachers' cultivation related with the process of realization of deep understanding of the

text. To what extent do the two interactive factors (reader and text) affect *meaningful reading*? Where should the instructional activities be focused on mostly? a) on the study of the structure of text b) on the activation of the student's Higher Order structures, which structuralize the text meaning? (reader's text) c) or should they have the same priority in teaching?

It is clear to the teachers that the aim of *meaningful reading* is the realization of a deep understanding of meaning (students garnering a comprehensive and broadly contextualized understanding of the text with which they are engaging) and development of critical thinking in the reader. This is also observed in the general result of the influence (a.) of the instructional activities (questions of general meaning and questions of meaningful linguistic and stylistic interpretation and reflection) which reveal a text's broader meaning according to its structuring elements (grammar) and (b.) of the instructional activities of activation of higher order structures of the elaboration of meaning.

Deep understanding contains both the meaning of understanding as well as the opportunity of data employment, the set of problems on text meaning, but also the active and interactive role of the reader in the building of meaning through the written text.

In a summarized way, I refer to the general trends of contemporary experiences in the teaching of meaningful reading:

Constructivism shifted the teachers' interest from the text to the students' mental mechanisms of text understanding (due to the level of difficulty of text comprehensibility and the indicators of students' readability). But it does not deny the role of the text. The question arises: Where should we seek the text meaning? In the writer's mind (text base)? In the reader's mind, who structures and builds the text meaning during the reading process? Or in the interaction between the reader and text/

Constructivists stick to the third thesis. According to the constructivists, understanding should be sought in the cutting point of the meaning of the reader, of the text and text content. (Schoenbach et al, 1999).

(Kern, 2000), refers to three trends:

- a) Teaching focused on the text (product-approach, text based),
- b) Teaching focused on the process (process-approach)
- c) Teaching focused on the genre of the text (genre-based approach).

That which is needed, according to Kern, is a trend which will have the reader at its epicenter (following an integrative, student-centered approach), but which will respond simultaneously to the interaction and interdependence of the textual product, of cognitive processes and of socio-cultural factors. Thus, a trend, which should be

focused on meaning, the same way as it is structured through the form in a cultural context. In recent years, we've observed trends of application of constructive and social-cultural models. More recently, we've seen the social-cognitive model in teaching of textual understanding being more widely embraced (Flower, 2003). The main place in the theoretical social-cognitive model is increasingly occupied by the teaching of process-genre based approach model (referred to Spandidakis, 2009). In addition to the procedures, knowledge and strategies necessary for text production,

Stress is also placed on the meaning of the text and its genre. Textual content, base and style represent concrete social-cultural characteristics of the location (time and place) in which the text was produced. The analysis of situating in context (both setting and contextualization) is necessary for the writer and the reader alike, in order to build the analogue meaning according to the situational context. In this regard, learning of knowledge and habits which are related with the text constitute a social activity, as the method by which repeated situations of communication are constructed. For example, the relationship between the author and the reader may be understood through the lens of a historical context as it relates to a specific community.

The scholars raise the question of what to teach students about meaningful reading. Pedagogical studies and instructional practices indicate that the students should learn text genres and how they are used in specific contexts of communication. They should also develop the skills, knowledge and strategies as instruments for the development of competent communication through different text genres and they should develop metacognitive skills in *meaningful reading*.

Students should be able to reflect, judge and evaluate a written text. They should use genres of text within the correct context of communication. They should utilize a critical approach towards the text and the reality to which the text refers. Before the students learn to write a certain text, they should learn that text's grammatical functions as a process of building the meaning and writing the text. According to the cognitive psychology and constructivism, the written text is conceptualized as a holistic process of building up meaning, in which understanding a text and writing a text are treated as two cognitive processes of constructing the overall meaning of the text.

Questionnaire

In the framework of a study on the most important factors which assist in the improvement of the level of critic thinking, the active meaningful learning capacity and meaningful reading of a school text and an extracurricular text, this questionnaire will serve as important information.

Your answers are completely anonymous and confidential.

Please, answer by circling the respective number for each of the following assertions:

A little = 1; Satisfactory = 2; Highly = 3.

No. of the question	Questions-Strategies	Little	Satisfactory	Highly
1	How much is the selection of reading texts represented in the subject matter of the Albanian language?			
1.a	Literary text	1	2	3
1.b	Non-literary text	1	2	3
2	How much do you think that the non literary text should be represented?			
2.a	Argumentative text	1	2	3
2.b	Advising text	1	2	3
2.c	Text of comparison-contrast	1	2	3
2.d	Descriptive-informative text	1	2	3
3	During the teaching of the line “reading” of the literary text show much do you think the following elements of meaningful reading influence in understanding of a given text?			
3.a	Text content and communication context. (macro dhe microcontext)	1	2	3
3.b	Text structure (history grammar)	1	2	3
3.c	Habits and strategies of text understanding	1	2	3
3.d	Comparison between two texts (from content and structure)	1	2	3
3.e	Style and stylistical language of the text	1	2	3
4	How much do you think that the questions of the school book of Albanian language develop the critic and creative thinking during reading?	1	2	3
5	How much do you think that through teaching of the line “understanding” are developed the habits of depth understanding?			
5.a	Comparison	1	2	3
5.b	Analysis –Synthesis	1	2	3
5.c	Self-arrangement of understanding	1	2	3
5.d	Judgment –Argumentation	1	2	3
5.e	Assessment			

Thank you for being a part of this study.

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